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Reliability control in IoT networks with a mixture of exponentials as interference model

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Abstract—In a context high density of connected objects with low latency constraints, ensuring global system coordination is not realistic. Under these conditions, the interference can vary significantly from one packet to another. We propose a method to choose a robust communication scheme in this type of environment. For this purpose, we model the interference by a mixture of exponentials. To ensure the reliability of the estimation of the mixture parameters, we use a bootstrap method. This allows us to choose the parameters of the transmission in order to ensure a probability of success on the transmitted packets.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the goals of 5G networks is to support low latency despite high device density. This combination of requirements is difficult to solve. Low latency and large number of devices make it difficult, if not impossible, to coordinate effectively between all the devices in the network. This limits the ability to share accurate channel status information. The consequence of imperfect coordination is the level of interference. Furthermore, to address a large number of objects, non-orthogonal multiple access is desirable but amplifies this negative effect.

Without knowing *a priori* the level of interference that will be present during the transmission of a packet, it is nevertheless important to choose the most suitable modulation and coding scheme for the transmitter. Our goal is to guarantee a probability of success on the next packets that are transmitted. The *signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio* (SINR) will be the criterion used to guarantee success. To guarantee this SINR at the receiver, a good knowledge of the interference distribution is essential.

This paper is structured around two contributions: (a) modelling interference and (b) estimating the minimum link quality that must be satisfied to guarantee the targeted success probability. It is organised as follows: Section II describes the system studied and presents

the assumptions used. The state of the art on interference modelling is presented in Section III-A. Section III-B presents the exponential mixing model and the estimation of its parameters. A *bootstrap* algorithm is proposed to evaluate the link quality and to choose the modulation and coding scheme to guarantee the good communication. Section IV presents the results obtained.

II. SYSTEM STUDIED

In many connected object applications, regular interval communications are not justified and sporadic communications, initiated when a particular event occurs, are more appropriate. Ensuring a degree of reliability in a transmitter-dense radio environment is extremely difficult, especially in an environment where interference is highly variable and difficult to predict. Moreover, if time constraints are also imposed, it is not feasible to coordinate all transmitters.

Rather than the LP-WAN star networks often implemented today (top of Fig. 1), to allow for controlled latencies it is more appropriate to organise a set of smaller sub-networks (bottom of Fig. 1). This is a solution called "in-X" subnetworks [1] in the industry. Each subnetwork coordinates its communications to manage delays and interference. However, two subnetworks are not coordinated with each other. As they access the same resources, they generate interference between subnetworks.

Each sub-network coordinates its communications. However, there is no coordination between the different networks which use the same resources. A user (Useful Signal in Fig. 2) will therefore access certain resource blocks according to his needs.

Some users on other subnets will simultaneously access the same resource block, generating interference:

$$I = \sum_{i \in \Omega_k} l(d_i) \cdot Q_i, \quad (1)$$

where d_i is the distance between the interferer i and the receiver under study, $l(d)$ is the channel attenuation as a function of distance; a classic example of a model is

Fig. 1: Network configuration. The sketches on the left represent the objects (black circles) and the access points (red squares). The sketches on the right are the same where the links connecting an object to its access point are added. Top: Massive Machine-Type Communications — only two access points are present; bottom: Ultra-reliable Low-Latency Communication — smaller sub-networks are created.

$l_{\gamma,\epsilon}(d) = d^\gamma \mathbb{I}_{d \geq \epsilon}(d)$, $d \in \mathbb{R}^+$ where γ is the path loss exponent, ϵ an interferer-free zone (no interferer can be closer than ϵ to the receiver : $\mathbb{I}_{d \geq \epsilon}(d) = 1$ if $d \geq \epsilon$ and 0 otherwise); Q_i includes propagation effects (multipath, *shadowing*) and the characteristics of the physical layer; Ω_k is the set of interferers on resource k .

Fig. 2: The desired user accesses three different resource blocks. From the other networks come interfering signals. The set of interferers is different on each block.

We make the following assumptions :

- Ω_k is constant over a resource block. This block corresponds to the transmission of a packet. This means in particular that the sum of noise plus interference is a Gaussian random process over a packet.
- On two different blocks, Ω_k and Ω_j are independent. In particular, this means that the variance of the interference will be different from one packet to another.
- Depending on the modulation and coding scheme, the transmission of a packet will be considered successful if the signal (S) to noise (N) ratio plus interference (I) is above a given threshold : $S/(I + N) > \tau$.

Each user then aims to ensure a success rate (T):

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\frac{S}{I + N} > \tau\right) \geq T. \quad (2)$$

III. INTERFERENCE MODELLING

A. State of the art

The specification of the probability density function of the interfering signal is an important issue, for example when calculating the maximum likelihood for designing an optimal receiver. Many works have shown that the interference term is not adequately modelled by a Gaussian distribution.

The first major contribution was made by Middleton [2], [3] who obtained fairly general expressions in series form by assuming Poisson distributed interference sources. However, this popular model remains difficult to use because of the infinite sums. Some approximations have been proposed by considering the predominant terms (mixture of Gaussian [4], ϵ -contaminated [5] when only two terms are considered). In more specific scenarios, such as ultra-wideband communications, distributions have been proposed empirically, justified by simulations, observations of the estimated probability density and/or gains in terms of bit error rate: Normal-Laplace mixture [6], Generalized Gaussian [7], Gaussian mixtures [8], Cauchy-Gaussian mixture [9]. Another frequently used class of models is the α -stable model, which finds its source in the spatial distribution of interferers [10].

In the context of the power of interference, a detailed study has been carried out by [11]. In the case of interferers distributed according to a homogeneous Poisson point process in an infinite radius network with no guard zone [10], the interfering power follows a totally skewed α -stable distribution ($\beta = 1$), α depends only on the channel attenuation and the dispersion δ of the other network characteristics (interferers density, radio channel fading, physical layer). Two recent experimental works have confirmed the impulsive nature of the interference, in ISM bands [12] and in 4G cellular networks in vehicular context [13].

To reflect the impulsiveness of the model we propose to use a mixture of exponentials. The mixture has the ability to represent the behaviour of the heavy tail obtained theoretically and experimentally (the rare appearance of large values). This choice allows an easier analytical derivation and the possibility to propose practical solutions for the design of communication links.

B. Exponential mixture model (EMM)

To model the interference we consider that on a resource block (see Fig. 2) the set of interferers Ω_i is constant. The interference, resulting from the sum of the

contributions of these interferers, can then be modelled by a Gaussian distribution. The power of the interference is then modelled by an exponential distribution. The probability density of an exponential distribution with parameter $a > 0$ is given by :

$$f(x; a) = a \exp(-ax), \quad x \geq 0. \quad (3)$$

As the set of interferers Ω_i varies from a transmitted packet to another, the parameter of the exponential distribution will also vary. The resulting distribution will consequently be a mixture of exponentials (MME), whose probability density can be expressed as:

$$f_Y(y) = \sum_{i=1}^N \pi_i f(y; a_i), \quad (4)$$

where N is the number of components in the mixture, $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, \dots, a_N)$ the component parameters and $\boldsymbol{\pi} = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_N) \in \mathbb{R}_+^N$ the respective weights, such that $\sum_{i=1}^N \pi_i = 1$. This model has been discussed in detail in [14].

The mixture of exponentials naturally adapts to the configuration of the "in-X" subnetworks. The access policy, based only on the knowledge of a single subnetwork and not taking into account the others, generates groups of interferers which will be modified at each transmission. The resulting mixture may have a limited number of components, depending in particular on the proximity of the closest active interferers. In the following we will limit the distributions to three components.

C. The Expectation - Maximization (EM) algorithm

It is crucial in the design of a wireless communication link to be able to estimate the parameters of the interference distribution. An EMM can be considered as a latent variable model [15] whose parameters $\boldsymbol{\pi}, \mathbf{a}$ can be estimated using the Expectation - Maximization (EM) algorithm [16], whose pseudo-code adapted to our context is presented in Algorithm 1.

D. Estimation of quantiles : Bootstrap

To ensure that the transmitted packets are received correctly, we must check (2). We assume that S is known (channel attenuation and transmit power are assumed to be known) and N is the receiver noise level. In order to know the link quality, we have to determine I , the interference power. However, this is not predictable from one packet to another. We therefore need to choose a modulation and coding scheme that will ensure a target success rate T and to do this we look for the threshold τ that will allow us to set the transmission scheme that should ensure a good performance at the obtained threshold.

Algorithm 1 EM POUR MME

Initialize : $a_i^0, \pi_i^0, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad p = 0$

while not converged **do**

E-step:

$$\varphi_i(\pi^p, a^p, y_j) = \frac{\pi_i^p a_i^p \exp(-a_i^p y_j)}{\sum_{k=1}^N \pi_k^p a_k^p \exp(-a_k^p y_j)}$$

M-step:

$$\pi_i^{p+1} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \varphi_i(a^p, \pi^p, y_j)}{n}$$

$$a_i^{p+1} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \varphi_i(\pi^p, a^p, y_j)}{\sum_{j=1}^n y_j \varphi_i(\pi^p, a^p, y_j)}$$

$p \rightarrow p + 1$

end while

return a^{p-1}, π^{p-1}

Checking (2) is in fact the same as determining the threshold x_T such that $\mathbb{P}(I \leq x_T) = T$. If we know the parameters of the MME, the target threshold x_T can be obtained by solving $\sum_{\ell=1}^R \pi_\ell \exp(-a_\ell x_T) = 1 - T$. However, the estimates of the parameters \mathbf{a} and $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ are inaccurate and it is desirable to evaluate the confidence interval and strengthen its estimate for a better performance guarantee.

Let $1 - \alpha$ be the desired confidence level, x_T the true (unknown) threshold and \hat{x}_T the estimated threshold. We want to ensure that $\mathbb{P}(x_T - \hat{x}_T > z) \leq 1 - \alpha$. The solution z corresponds to the excess that should be incorporated in the estimate of x_T . In other words, the appropriate threshold is given by $\tau' = \hat{x}_T + z$. We can consider \hat{x}_T as an estimate of the desired threshold. A confidence interval can be estimated by the bootstrap method [17].

Bootstrap is based on creating a collection of several samples from a single larger one. These repeated samples are called resamples (K). The solution implemented is presented in Algorithm 2.

IV. RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The proposed protocol to choose the transmission scheme is as follows:

- The access point listens to the environment for a given time T_D and collects n_D noise power samples.
- It estimates \mathbf{a} et $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ (Algorithm 1), calculates the threshold \hat{x}_T and improves the estimate by the *bootstrap* procedure (Algorithm 2).
- It transmits the threshold x_T to the transmitter (the only transmission needed in the downlink).

Algorithm 2 Bootstrap

Initialize : $D = A$ set of samples of the EMM.
Find \hat{x}_T such that :

$$\sum_{l=1}^R \pi_l \exp(-a_l \hat{x}_T) = 1 - T.$$

for $i = 1$ **to** $p \in \mathbb{N}$ **do**

Draw p sets of samples $(K_1, K_2 \dots K_p)$ from D .

This yields new estimates : $\hat{x}_T^1, \hat{x}_T^2 \dots \hat{x}_T^p$.

$$\Delta^i = \hat{x}_T^i - \hat{x}_T.$$

end for

Select the smallest z such that :

$$\mathbb{P}(\Delta^i > z) \leq 1 - \alpha \iff \frac{1}{p} \sum_{i=1}^p \mathbb{I}_{\{\Delta^i > z\}} \leq 1 - \alpha.$$

return $\tau' = \hat{x}_T + z$.

- The transmitter chooses its modulation and coding scheme that will allow it to guarantee the target SINR and thus the required quality of service.

In the simulations we use $n_D = 500$ or 1000 as the number of samples of D and $n_K = 100$ as the number of samples of each resampling $K_i, \forall i = 1 \dots p \in \mathbb{N}$, for the bootstrap. We choose a probability of success $T = 0.99$. To calculate the probability of success shown in Fig. 3, we determine over 1000 realisations the number of packets where the interfering power is less than x_T (assuming the parameters of the interference distribution are known), \hat{x}_T (the estimated threshold without bootstrapping) and τ' (the estimated threshold with bootstrapping) respectively. This represents the success rate of the packet transmission.

Fig. 3: Success rate (theoretical, with and without bootstrap) of packet transmission ($n_D = 500$ and $n_K = 100$)

The proposed method achieves the objectives set: the probability of success is well above the target probability, which is not the case with the estimated parameters and

Fig. 4: Success rate (theoretical, with and without bootstrap) of packet transmission ($n_D = 1000$ and $n_K = 100$)

would not be the case with the theoretical parameters either. The uncertainty due to highly variable interference distributions is therefore well taken into account by the bootstrap method, which therefore seems quite relevant in the context of impulsive interference.

The proposed method allows, with a reduced information exchange, to take into account the statistical properties of interference and to guarantee a target success probability. This is crucial in communications requiring reliability within a controlled time frame. Moreover, the access point is constantly listening and can regularly revise the model parameters and the threshold transmitted to the transmitter to take into account the temporal evolution of the environment. There are still many ways to optimise the proposed system.

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